

LEFT SIDED CONGESTIVE HEART FAILURE IN CANINES: AN OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Left sided heart failure is a quite common in Indian and Exotic dog breeds. Prognosis of the condition is quite poor unless proper management and care is not taken. The affected dogs are mainly seen with the signs like coughing, fatigue, lethargy, weakness, dyspnoea which can have numerous causes like valvular disease, parasitic or bacterial endocarditis, arrhythmias or dilated cardiomyopathy. There are various treatment and medications available for the condition but once the critical period of the pathogenesis has surpassed, the condition will lead to death of the animal. This article is an overview of how left side heart failure condition in canines occur, diagnosis, treatment, and management.

Keywords: Left sided heart failure, Exotic dog breeds, CHF, pulmonary edema

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